

Complex Endoscopic Retrieval of an Embedded PCSEMS in a Patient with Recurrent Cholangitis: A Case Experience.

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Case Presentation

65 years old female patient underwent lap cholecystectomy 2018 and developed OJ in 2021 ERCP done with insertion of PCSEMS as malignant lower CBD stricture but EUS with FNB revealed benign stricture then patient presented to our Mahalla liver teaching hospital with OJ and cholangitis in 2023 we do ERCP with insertion of FCSEMS in migrated embedded PCSEMS.

Stent in stent technique for removal of PCSEMS

But we failed for removal and transfer the patient for surgical exploration but surgery refused exploration. Patient returned now with severe cholangitis we do ERCP and our plan to put plastic stent inside PCSEMS but the patient was lucky this time

ERCP reveale multiple stones inside stent.

Extraction was done with dormia basket and washing then we use foreign body and fluoroscopy for removal of PCMS.

Insertion of double pigtail stent with good biliary flow.

Fig 1

Fig 2

Fig 3

Fig 4

Fig 5

Fig 6

Medtronic